

STREAMLINED GERIATRIC AND ONCOLOGICAL EVALUATION BASED ON
 IC TECHNOLOGY
 FOR HOLISTIC PATIENT-ORIENTED HEALTHCARE MANAGEMENT
 FOR OLDER MULTIMORBID PATIENTS

HORIZON 2020 PROGRAMME – TOPIC H2020-SC1-BHC-24-2020
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**D1.2: DATASET OF SYMPTOMS AND PROMS FOR SPECIFIC CANCER
 TYPES AND GENDER**

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V1.3	2022-03-10	Marije Hamaker	Dataset reference from ZENODO added

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Executive Summary

This deliverable reports on the development of a core dataset of symptoms and patient reported outcome measures (PROMs) for specific cancer types and gender. The dataset of symptoms and PROMs are also specific for various treatment types (such as surgery, chemotherapy, radiation therapy, and targeted therapy). Data regarding symptoms and PROMs will be reported directly from patients by the patient app Holis and made available to the health care professional consortium to support oncologic decision making and determine how the patient is best supported through their oncologic treatment trajectory and follow-up. After literature review, input was received from an expert panel of medical specialists, nurses and other health care professionals with a background in geriatric medicine or involved in cancer treatment for the four cancer types included in Geronte (breast, prostate, lung and colorectal cancer). Through an iterative process, it was decided which symptoms and PROMs were relevant and how these were best captured in data to provide to the health care professional consortium. This resulted in a list of 28 relevant symptoms and PROMs to be included in the dataset provided to the health care professional consortium based on reports from the patient. We also developed a protocol for the frequency of reporting depending on treatment type and the precise location of the patient in their treatment trajectory.

Attainment of the objectives and explanation of deviations

In the Grant Agreement, we proposed to select 5 symptoms, 5 indicators of destabilized comorbidities, and 3 indicators of functional decline that would be used for monitoring. However, given the heterogeneity within the population of older patients with multimorbidity and cancer, it was not possible to allocate the set of 18 core symptoms and 10 additional symptoms depending on cancer or treatment, to one of these three categories (symptoms of cancer, indicator of destabilized comorbidity, or indicator of functional decline). Thus, the selected symptoms were clustered together without further link to their origin. However, we did achieve the minimum of 13 symptoms to be used for monitoring.

Justification for delay in deliverable submission

The objectives related to this deliverable have been achieved on time and as scheduled in Annexe 1 (Description of the Action Part A) of the Grant Agreement N°945218.

1. Introduction

1.1. GERONTE and its objectives

GERONTE is a 5-year research and innovation project (April 2021 to Mars 2026) funded by the European Union within the framework of the H2020 Research and Innovation programme, in response to the health societal challenge topic SC1-BHC-24-2020 “Healthcare interventions for the management of the elderly multimorbid patient”. The overall aim of GERONTE is to improve quality of life - defined as well-being on three levels: global health status, physical functioning and social functioning- for older multimorbid patients, while reducing overall costs of care. To this end, GERONTE will co-design, test, and prepare for deployment an innovative cost-effective patient-centred holistic health management system, hereafter referred to as the GERONTE intervention. GERONTE intervention will rely on an ICT based application for real-time collection and integration of standardised clinical and home patient-reported data. GERONTE intervention will be demonstrated in the context of care of multimorbid patients having cancer as a dominant morbidity, and be adaptable to any other combination of morbidities.

Objectives

- O1: INFORMATION** gather the stakeholders and data needed for patient-centred and multi-actor complex decision-making process and management
- O2: TOOLS** develop ICT tools for the GERONTE intervention to be implemented
- O3: METHODS** develop socio-economic methods for evaluating the impacts of the implementation of the GERONTE intervention
- O4: DEMONSTRATION** demonstrate in 16 study sites from three EU countries the feasibility and effectiveness of the GERONTE intervention
- O5: REPLICATION** develop recommendations for the replication of GERONTE best practices in all European health systems
- O6: ENGAGEMENT** engage all stakeholders by co-designing the GERONTE intervention

1.2. Rationale

Deliverable D1.4 is part of work-package 1 which supports GERONTE objective O1: INFORMATION. An important component of Geronte is to monitor symptoms and PROMs during the treatment trajectory for cancer in order to catch early signs of destabilization of the patient due to symptoms, destabilized comorbidities or functional decline. This may lead to early interventions by the APN to prevent further decline. This deliverable describes the process of developing a list of symptoms and PROMs for specific cancer types and gender that are relevant to oncology care and treatment monitoring. The list is made for patient report from the patient app.

2. Developing dataset of symptoms and PROMs for specific cancer types and gender

2.1. Literature review

We performed a systematic literature search to identify papers on self-management and self-monitoring interventions during cancer treatment for older patients with cancer. However, the search strategy failed to identify all relevant papers, in particular because self-monitoring has mostly been performed in younger patients with cancer in previous studies, and no studies were specifically done in the older population. Studies also differed between self-monitoring and self-management, and the majority of studies on self-monitoring were in relation to cancer screening interventions. We therefore changed our strategy and based our symptoms and PROMs on (1) experiences from our partner institution in GerOnTe (Katholieke Univeriteit Leuven) which has a monitoring system in use already^{1,2} and (2) key randomized trials in the field that have been published in the recent years³⁻⁵. An overview of the literature that was included can be found in Annexe 1.

2.2. Expert panel input

A panel of experts was established, including medical specialists, nurses and other health care professionals with a background in geriatric medicine or involved in cancer treatment for the four cancer types included in Geronte (breast, prostate, lung and colorectal cancer).

In a series of monthly surveys, these experts were asked to provide their input on the relevance of which symptoms and PROMs were most relevant for decision making and follow-up of patients.

Answers to the survey were subsequently compiled, compared with findings from literature review, and taken forward to the next survey for further fine-tuning.

Each round included between 35 and 39 participants across a range of different backgrounds (doctors, nurses) and a range of specialisms (medical oncology, surgery, radiotherapy, pulmonology, urology, geriatrics). Mean age was 47 and respondents had a mean of 17 years in clinical practice.

Based on the literature review, a list of 53 symptoms and PROMS and the following questions (1) not relevant to monitor (2) relevant for all patients, both during treatment and follow-up (3) only relevant during treatment, and (4) only relevant for specific cancer types. In the next round, the experts were asked to state which symptoms and PROMs they prioritized. Results can be found in Annexe 2. Based on this feedback, a core set of 18 symptoms and PROMs were included to monitor for all patients, and additional symptoms and PROMS were collected for specific cancer types and according to gender and treatment type.

2.3 Monitoring of symptoms and PROMs in the cancer treatment trajectory

In the Grant Agreement, we proposed to select 5 symptoms, 5 indicators of destabilized comorbidities, and 3 indicators of functional decline that would be used for monitoring. However, given the heterogeneity within the population of older patients with multimorbidity and cancer, it was not possible to allocate the set of 18 symptoms that were selected by the expert panel specifically to one of these three categories (symptoms of cancer, indicator of destabilized comorbidity, or indicator of functional decline. For example, dyspnea could be a symptom of lung cancer, but also an indicator of destabilized heart failure. Fatigue could be a symptom, a sign of destabilized heart failure and an indicator of functional decline. The symptoms and PROMs were linked to the established comorbidity profiles. See illustration below.

	Cancer- or treatment-related symptoms	Signs of functional decline	Signs of destabilized comorbidity				
			Profile 1 Cardio-vascular, metabolic & pulmonary disease	Profile 2 Disability, dependency and caregiver burden	Profile 3 Psychosocial health and cognitive impairment	Profile 4 Nutritional status and digestive system disease	Profile 5 Concurrent cancer
ALL PATIENTS							
Dyspnoea	X		X				X
Diarrhoea	X					X	X
Vomiting	X					X	
Nausea	X					X	
Daily activities limited by bowel/urinary problems	X	X		X		X	
Poor appetite	X					X	X
Weight change	X	X	X			X	
Pain	X			X			
Fever/feeling ill	X						
Fatigue	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Trouble sleeping	X				X		
Trouble remembering/thinking; confusion	X	X			X		
Feeling depressed or irritable	X				X		
Feeling nervous, worried or uncertain	X				X		
Change in mobility	X	X		X			
Unsteady on your feet/falls	X	X		X			
Forced to spend time in bed	X	X	X	X	X		
Need help with daily activities	X	X		X			

Additionally, specific cancer types and treatment warrant specific monitoring:

<i>Chemotherapy</i> Sore/dry mouth Tingling hand/feet Rash/skin issue	<i>After surgery/radiotherapy</i> Wound problems Rash/skin issues Bloody stools or mucus (colorectal and prostate only)	<i>After ostomy:</i> Ostomy issues	<i>Lung cancer</i> Cough Cough up blood
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An important comment received in asserting the relevance of symptoms and PROMs was that only the presence of the symptom/PROM was not sufficient; additional information on the severity of a symptom as well as symptom development may affect an oncological decision or the treatment trajectory. During the expert meeting, we therefore discussed which cut-offs to use for symptoms and PROMs and the frequency of monitoring. We based our grading of symptom severity on the study by Basch and colleagues³. Because of multiple possible combinations in individual patients, we

decided that we need to tailor the list of symptoms to the individual patients with regards to cancer type, treatment type, and gender. Furthermore, the frequency of monitoring will vary according to the location of the patient in the treatment trajectory. It was therefore decided that the monitoring will be customized by the advanced practice nurse (APN) in the patient app based on the individual cancer- and treatment types. The symptoms and PROMs are linked to self-management recommendations in the app, as described in deliverable 1.4. – DATASET OF SELF-MANAGEMENT RECOMMENDATIONS FOR PATIENT-DRIVEN IMPROVEMENT OF INDEPENDENT LIVING.

The final symptoms and PROMs and cut-off values for notification to contact the APN are specified in annexe 3, 4, 5 and 6. There are three separate list: one for symptoms, one for destabilized comorbidities, and one for functional decline, as well as specific lists for treatment trajectory, treatment type and cancer type. These can also be found in the dataset GERDAT006 “Dataset of symptoms and proms for specific cancer types and gender” (published online at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6342645>). There was a need to extend the lists from the minimum 13 items (originally split into 5 symptoms, 5 indicators of destabilized comorbidities, and 3 indicators of functional decline) in our deliverables in order to cover all the relevant aspects in the monitoring of patients during the trial.

2.4 Symptoms and PROMs for gender

Based on the feedback from the survey and the discussion about symptoms and PROMs for gender in the group of experts, we decided to not make a distinction for gender in the monitoring of patients with colorectal cancer or lung cancer. For prostate cancer the symptoms and PROMs will be specific for males, and for breast cancer the vast majority of patients will be women. However, even for these cancer types the symptoms and PROMs cannot be considered to be gender specific. For signs of destabilized comorbidities and functional decline there is also no distinction for monitoring according to gender. When capturing destabilization or increase of symptoms, the patients are their own controls, and destabilization is related to their baseline functional status which is independent from gender.

3. Conclusion

This document reports on the development of a core dataset of symptoms and PROMs data that need to be reported by patients and monitored by the HPC during the treatment trajectory to support oncologic decision making and determine how the patient is best supported through their oncologic treatment trajectory and follow-up. The dataset will be tailored to cancer type, treatment type, and gender. Gender will be taken into account as some cancers are more prevalent in female patients (breast cancer) while prostate cancer affects only male patients. The list of symptoms and PROMs overlap with regards to monitoring of symptoms, destabilized comorbidities, and functional decline.

Annexe 1: Papers assessed in symptoms and PROMs literature review

1. Coolbrandt A, Muylaert K, Vandeneede E, Dooms C, Wildiers H. Real-time symptom management in the context of a remote symptom-monitoring system: prospective process evaluation and cross-sectional survey to explore clinical relevance. *Support Care Cancer* 2021; **29**(6): 3401-8.
2. Coolbrandt A, Muylaert K, Vandeneede E, Dooms C, Wildiers H. Remote System for Daily Symptom Monitoring During Systemic Anticancer Treatment: Patient Acceptance, Usability, and Compliance. *Cancer Nurs* 2021.
3. Basch E, Deal AM, Kris MG, et al. Symptom Monitoring With Patient-Reported Outcomes During Routine Cancer Treatment: A Randomized Controlled Trial. *J Clin Oncol* 2016; **34**(6): 557-65.
4. Maguire R, Fox PA, McCann L, et al. The eSMART study protocol: a randomised controlled trial to evaluate electronic symptom management using the advanced symptom management system (ASyMS) remote technology for patients with cancer. *BMJ Open* 2017; **7**(5): e015016.
5. Maguire R, McCann L, Kotronoulas G, et al. Real time remote symptom monitoring during chemotherapy for cancer: European multicentre randomised controlled trial (eSMART). *Bmj* 2021; **374**: n1647.

Annexe 2: Quality of life questionnaires used to compile the list and method for symptom monitoring

General quality of life questionnaires for patients with cancer

Functional living with cancer

Functional assessment of cancer therapy (FACT) – general

European organisation of Research and Treatment of Cancer – QLQ-C30

Quality of life questionnaires for older patients with cancer

European organisation of Research and Treatment of Cancer – ELD14

Quality of life questionnaires for patients with prostate cancer

Functional assessment of cancer therapy (FACT) – prostate

European organisation of Research and Treatment of Cancer – PR25

Quality of life questionnaires for patients with breast cancer

Functional assessment of cancer therapy (FACT) – breast

European organisation of Research and Treatment of Cancer – BR23

Quality of life questionnaires for patients with lung cancer

Functional assessment of cancer therapy (FACT) – Lung

European organisation of Research and Treatment of Cancer – LC13

Quality of life questionnaires for patients with colorectal cancer

Functional assessment of cancer therapy (FACT) – Colorectal

European organisation of Research and Treatment of Cancer – CR29

Quality of life questionnaires for patients undergoing radiotherapy

European organisation of Research and Treatment of Cancer – PRT23

General quality of life questionnaires

36-Item Short Form Survey (SF-36)

12-Item Short Form Survey (SF-12)

EQ5D

Edmonton symptom assessment scale (ESAS)

Annexe 3: Relevance of symptoms and PROMs for monitoring according to expert panel

Percentages represent the proportion of participants stating that the symptom/PROM condition would likely or very likely be relevant to monitor during the care trajectory. Items were not carried forward to the next round of the survey if they scored less than 50% or higher.

Symptom/PROM	Not relevant to monitor	Relevant for all patients
dissatisfied with body	67%	33%
performing strenuous activities	54%	38%
satisfied with sexual life	50%	50%
sweats	46%	31%
trouble remembering	36%	64%
trouble thinking/concentrating	36%	50%
uncertainty	36%	50%
trouble sleeping	29%	64%
anxiety/feeling nervous	29%	57%
worrying/upset	29%	57%
fatigue	21%	71%
need help with household chores, groceries, medications	21%	71%
unsteady on your feet/dizziness	21%	57%
depressed/feeling low	14%	86%
decreased/change in mobility (walk, rise from chair, stairs)	14%	79%
need help with self care (dressing, washing, toileting)	14%	79%
poor appetite	7%	86%
weight loss	7%	93%
dyspnea	0%	100%
falls	0%	100%
pain	0%	93%
confusion	0%	93%
fever/shivering/feeling ill	0%	79%
daily activities limited because of bowel or urinary problems	21%	64%
forced to spend time in bed	14%	71%
feeling irritable	46%	31%
teary eyes	46%	8%
palpitations	23%	38%
bloated feeling	58%	25%
hair loss	43%	7%
headache	36%	43%
cough	36%	36%
trouble swallowing	7%	64%
nausea	0%	64%

vomiting	0%	64%
tingling hand/feet	23%	23%
stomatitis/sore mouth/dry mouth	8%	31%
bloody stools or mucus	0%	69%
rash/skin issues	8%	25%
frequent bowel movements/urination	43%	29%
diarrhoea	0%	36%
edema/swelling	0%	64%
release of gas	62%	8%
dysuria	38%	31%
urinary incontinence	43%	29%
constipation	14%	36%
cough up blood	0%	71%
wound problems (healing, bleeding)	0%	54%
fecal incontinence	29%	29%
weight gain	21%	43%
problems with incontinence aid/stoma care	29%	29%
Stoma leakage	21%	36%
Sore skin stoma	14%	43%

Annexe 4: List of symptoms and PROMs that were considered relevant to monitor for all patients, frequency of monitoring during treatment and cut-offs for when the patient is recommended to contact the APN

Symptom	Frequency of monitoring	Cut-off for notification
Dyspnoea	Daily	2 days grade 3 Any rise of 2 points
Diarrhoea	Daily	2 days grade 3
Vomiting	Daily	2 days grade 3
Nausea	Weekly	2 weeks grade 3
Daily activities limited by bowel/urinary problems	Weekly	2 weeks grade 3
Poor appetite	Weekly	2 weeks grade 3
Weight change	Weekly	+/- ≥ 2 kg or change in fit of clothes
Pain	Daily	2 days grade 3
Fever/feeling ill	Daily	2 days grade 3 Any temp >38C
Fatigue	Weekly	2 weeks grade 3
Trouble remembering/thinking; confusion	Monthly	Any grade 3 Any rise of 2 points
Forced to spend time in bed	Weekly	2 weeks grade 3
Need help with daily activities	Monthly	Any grade 3 Any rise of 2 points

Annexe 5: List of symptoms and PROMs that are indicators of destabilized comorbidities for all patients

Indicator	Frequency of monitoring	Cut-off for notification
Dyspnoea	Daily	2 days grade 3 Any rise of 2 points
Diarrhoea	Daily	2 days grade 3
Vomiting	Daily	2 two days in a row/more than 3/7 per week
Nausea	Weekly	2 days grade 3
Daily activities limited by bowel/urinary problems	Weekly	2 weeks grade 3
Poor appetite	Weekly	2 weeks grade 3
Weight change	Weekly	+/- ≥ 2 kg or change in fit of clothes
Pain	Daily	2 days grade 3
Fatigue	Weekly	2 weeks grade 3
Trouble sleeping	Weekly	2 weeks grade 3
Trouble remembering/thinking; confusion	Monthly	Any grade 3 Any rise of 2 points
Feeling depressed or irritable	Monthly	Any grade 3
Feeling nervous, worried or uncertain	Monthly	Any grade 3
Change in mobility	Monthly	Any grade 3 Any rise of 2 points
Unsteady on your feet/falls	Monthly	Any grade 3 Any rise of 2 points
Forced to spend time in bed	Weekly	2 weeks grade 3
Need help with daily activities	Monthly	Any grade 3 Any rise of 2 points

Annexe 6: List of symptoms and PROMs that are indicators of functional decline for all patients

Indicator	Frequency of monitoring	Cut-off for notification
Daily activities limited by bowel/urinary problems	Weekly	2 weeks grade 3
Weight change	Weekly	+/- ≥ 2 kg or change in fit of clothes
Fatigue	Weekly	2 weeks grade 3
Trouble remembering/thinking; confusion	Monthly	Any grade 3 Any rise of 2 points
Change in mobility	Monthly	Any grade 3 Any rise of 2 points
Unsteady on your feet/falls	Monthly	Any grade 3 Any rise of 2 points
Forced to spend time in bed	Weekly	2 weeks grade 3
Need help with daily activities	Monthly	Any grade 3 Any rise of 2 points

Additionally, specific cancer types and treatment types warrant specific monitoring:

<i>Chemotherapy</i>	<i>After surgery/radiotherapy</i>	<i>After ostomy:</i>	<i>Lung cancer</i>
Sore/dry mouth	Wound problems	Ostomy issues	Cough
Tingling hand/feet	Rash/skin issues		Cough up blood
Rash/skin issue	Bloody stools or mucus (colorectal and prostate only)		

Annexe 7: Symptoms and PROMs in patient app according to treatment trajectory and cancer and treatment type

1) App daily during treatment

Asked in all patients during "active treatment", except for hormonal treatment patients	
Core symptoms	Contact health care provider
Dyspnoea	Any very severe 1 day, AND/OR severe 2 days AND/OR any rise of ≥ 2 points
Diarrhoea	Any almost constantly 1 day, AND/OR frequently 2 days
Vomiting	Any very severe 1 day, AND/OR severe 2 days
Pain	Any very severe 1 day, AND/OR severe 2 days
Fever/feeling ill	Any temperature ≥ 38 C
only asked in chemotherapy patients	
Chemotherapy	
Sore/dry mouth	Any very severe 1 day, AND/OR severe 2 days

2 App weekly during treatment

Asked in all patients during active treatment	
Core symptoms	Contact health care provider
Nausea	Any very severe 1 week, AND/OR severe 2 weeks
Daily activities limited by bowel/urinary problems	Any very severe 1 week, AND/OR severe 2 weeks
Poor appetite	Any very severe 1 week, AND/OR severe 2 weeks
Weight change	Change of +/- 2 kg in 2 weeks
Fatigue	Any very severe 1 week, AND/OR severe 2 weeks
Trouble sleeping	Any very severe 1 week, AND/OR severe 2 weeks
Forced to spend time in bed	Any almost constantly 1 week, AND/OR frequently 2 weeks
only asked in chemotherapy patients during active treatment	
Chemotherapy	
Tingling hand/feet	Any very severe 1 week, AND/OR severe 2 weeks

Rash/skin issues	Any very severe 1 week, AND/OR severe 2 weeks
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3) App monthly during treatment

Core symptoms	Contact health care provider
Trouble remembering/thinking; confusion	Any severe/very severe
Feeling depressed or irritable	Any severe/very severe
Feeling nervous, worried or uncertain	Any severe/very severe
Change in mobility	Any severe/very severe
Unsteady on your feet	Any severe/very severe
Falls	Any occasionally, frequently or almost constantly
Need help with daily activities	Any frequently or almost constantly

Test

4) App weekly after treatment

Core symptoms	Contact health care provider
Dyspnoea	Any severe/very severe, any rise of ≥ 2 points
Diarrhoea	Any almost constantly 1 week, AND/OR frequently 2 weeks
Vomiting	Any very severe 1 week, AND/OR severe 2 weeks
Daily activities limited by bowel/urinary problems	Any very severe 1 week, AND/OR severe 2 weeks
Poor appetite	Any very severe 1 week, AND/OR severe 2 weeks
Pain	Any very severe 1 week, AND/OR severe 2 weeks

4) App monthly after treatment

Core symptoms	Contact health care provider
Fatigue	Any severe/very severe
Trouble sleeping	Any severe/very severe
Trouble remembering/thinking; confusion	Any severe/very severe
Feeling depressed or irritable	Any severe/very severe
Feeling nervous, worried or uncertain	Any severe/very severe
Change in mobility	Any severe/very severe
Unsteady on your feet	Any severe/very severe
Falls	Any occasionally, frequently or almost constantly
Forced to spend time in bed	Any frequently or almost constantly

Need help with daily activities	Any frequently or almost constantly
Weight change	Change of +/- 3 kg in 1 month

5) Other symptoms specific for cancer types and treatment types

Treatment options			
Stoma	yes/no		
Surgery	yes/no		
Radiotherapy	yes/no		
Chemotherapy	yes/no		
Immunotherapy	yes/no		
Hormone therapy (active treatment? No daily symptoms)	yes/no		>during active treatment no daily symptoms
Targeted therapy	yes/no		
Other therapy	yes/no		
Disease or treatment specific symptoms			
	Asked in which patients?	During treatment	After treatment
Bloody stools	[CRC] OR [prostate AND radiation]	weekly	Monthly
Mucus in stool	[CRC] OR [prostate AND radiation]	weekly	Monthly
Skin issues/rash	[Chemotherapy] OR [radiation therapy]	weekly	
Cough	Lung cancer	weekly	Monthly
Cough up blood	Lung cancer	weekly	
Hot flushes	Removed		
Wound problems	[Surgery] OR [Stoma]	weekly	
stoma issues	[Stoma AND CRC]	weekly	Monthly

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